

EARTHONE UPDATE | Winter 25/26

Coordinator's message

Silvia Uribe (UPM) on EARTHONE's first year

Throughout 2025, EARTHONE focused on establishing strong foundations. Stakeholder engagement across regions, detailed methodology design for each pilot site, and the setup of the project's technical architecture were among the key milestones. Legal and socio-economic assessments are complete, and environmental data collection is now underway.

"Our focus now is on refining tools and ensuring they respond to the challenges users face in practice." — Silvia Uribe

[Full recap of the year](#)

Co-creation Workshops

Insights from Italy, Greece, and beyond

In 2025, EARTHONE held three co-creation workshops (in Italy, Greece, and online) to gather input from land managers, researchers, and public stakeholders. The published findings now guide the development of the project's tools, highlighting key priorities such as usability, localisation, data integration, and explainable AI.

[Insights from the workshops](#)

EARTHONE in action

Recent developments of the project

EARTHONE team advanced field research and analysis across pilot sites and partner institutions. [At Sasse Rami in Italy](#), researchers examined soybean performance, soil conditions and microclimatic variation within a mature agroforestry

system. In Spain, [new phenological cameras installed at Tablas de Daimiel](#) are now providing continuous visual records of vegetation dynamics. [UPM, Bremen and Twente](#) also met for a focused technical exchange on climate modelling and phenology to reinforce coordinated work and ensure policy-relevant outputs.

Installation of phenological cameras in the Tablas de Daimiel National Park

EARTHONE team members using these tools as part of the demonstration

EARTHONE at events

Presenting work, listening to others

- **European Researchers' Night 2025** (Nicosia, Cyprus)
The Cyprus Institute introduced EARTHONE to a public audience, highlighting the project's climate-adaptive tools for agriculture.
- **EUROSOIL 2025** (Seville, Spain)
Vasileios Antoniadis (University of Thessaly) presented research from Pilot 2 (Zagora, Greece), examining how land-use change from forest to agriculture affects soil carbon and fertility.
- **RE4GREEN EU Social Lab** (Bonn, Germany)
EARTHONE team members joined discussions on vertical farming, bioeconomy, and responsible innovation, connecting with researchers from diverse disciplines.
- [MONALISA Clustering Workshop](#) (Bari, Italy)
The team contributed to dialogues on governance, monitoring, and policy links for soil restoration under the EU Mission Soil initiative.

Vasileios Antoniadis at EUROSOIL 2025

MONALISA clustering workshop

Growing synergies

New collaboration between EU projects on soil and climate resilience

On 30 October 2025, EARTHONE joined a Synergy Meeting with Horizon Europe projects working on sustainable land use, soil health, and climate adaptation. The meeting launched a collaboration **AgroTech Hub Cluster** focused on knowledge exchange and co-organised activities, such as an upcoming webinar series.

Participating projects:

[AgRimate](#) · [Agrarian](#) · [Climate Farm Demo](#) · [ENFORCE](#) · [EARTHONE](#) · [LandShift](#) · [MONALISA](#) · [Nemesis](#) · [NOSTRADAMUS](#) · [OpenAgri](#) · [TERRASAFE](#)

[See all the synergies](#)

Take a look at some of our partners:

[LandShift](#)

Works across five European Living Spaces to co-develop nature-based solutions for climate-resilient land management. Combining Earth Observation, AI, and stakeholder co-design, LandShift aims to balance mitigation, food security, and biodiversity. [Read their latest newsletter](#)

[MONALISA](#)

A Mission Soil project tackling land degradation and desertification through co-designed solutions across six Mediterranean case studies. Its main output is a multi-module Decision Support System.

[Nemesis](#)

Regenerates soil health across the Mediterranean through Living Labs that co-create and test solutions tailored to local contexts in areas such as soil-water management and biodiversity.

[TERRASAFE](#)

Supports rural communities with innovations like hydrogels, biochar-compost, artificial soils, and real-time soil sensors to prevent desertification in Southern Europe and North Africa.

Partners' news

MONALISA – Call for Contributions

The MONALISA project is inviting LDD experts to participate in its survey on effective practices to combat land degradation and desertification, helping strengthen the evidence base for restoration strategies.

[Complete the survey](#)

If you are interested in joining the activities to combat land degradation and desertification, the MONALISA [Community of Knowledge](#) is a platform for experts and stakeholders to connect, exchange insights and contribute to advancing sustainable land management.

NOSTRADAMUS – Why We Need Earth Observation

In the face of climate uncertainty and environmental stress, Earth Observation (EO) is key to smarter land-use decisions. The **NOSTRADAMUS** project combines EO with socio-economic and field data—processed through cloud and edge computing—to deliver actionable insights for agriculture and policy. From crop health to drought risks, EO helps optimise yields while reducing environmental impact.

[Read the full article](#)

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